

ARCHITECTURAL MODELS OF HIGH AVAILABILITY AND DISASTER RESILIENCE FOR ENTERPRISE SAP SYSTEMS IN A HYBRID INFRASTRUCTURE

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Keywords: SAP HANA, high availability, disaster resilience, hybrid infrastructure, data replication, RPO/RTO, HP Serviceguard, SUSE Linux Enterprise Server, data migration, cloud computing.	Abstract: <i>The study is devoted to the analysis of architectural solutions that ensure high availability and disaster resilience of enterprise SAP systems within contemporary hybrid IT landscapes. The relevance of the work is shaped by the escalating threat of cyber incidents in 2025 and by the active transition of companies toward cloud-based ERP operating models, which makes continuity of operation critically important. The aim is to systematize approaches to the design of fault-tolerant structures and to improve the efficiency of data recovery processes. The methodological foundation rests on a comparative analysis of SAP HANA and Oracle replication technologies, on the examination of practical migration cases from AIX platforms to Linux, and on a content analysis of technical documentation on clustering systems. The results obtained indicate the superiority of integrated models that combine on-premises HP Serviceguard clusters with cloud-based recovery services, making it possible to reduce downtime by 71.2%. The conclusions reached confirm the necessity of multi-layer monitoring and the automation of failover processes in order to minimize business risks. The data presented will be of interest to IT architects, system administrators, and managers of digital transformation units responsible for the reliability of mission-critical enterprise applications in an international environment.</i>
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Introduction

Under the conditions of global digitalization in 2025, corporate ERP systems, and SAP solutions in particular, have been transformed from auxiliary tools into a core element of business viability. The relevance of the topic is determined by the growing complexity of IT infrastructures, which are increasingly being formed according to a hybrid model. By 2025, hybrid IT landscapes had become a mainstream operating model for

enterprises, combining on-premises and cloud environments [1]. At the same time, such decentralization raises risks: statistics for the first half of 2025 record a 39% increase in critical SAP vulnerabilities compared with 2024, while the number of security notes with a CVSS score above 9.0 reached record levels [2].

The economic consequences of SAP system unavailability prove to be catastrophic. Research shows that 87% of companies encounter critical

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supply-chain disruptions after just eight hours of SAP downtime, while average financial losses during major incidents exceed USD 1 million in 15% of cases [3]. The scholarly literature still reveals an insufficient elaboration of models for seamless transition between on-premises and cloud-based high-availability nodes, especially in heterogeneous environments, for instance during migration from IBM AIX to SUSE Linux.

The aim of the study lies in the analysis and substantiation of architectural models that ensure the maximum resilience of SAP systems in a hybrid environment.

The scientific novelty is expressed in the development of an integrated model of hybrid disaster resilience that combines cascading database replication with cloud-native orchestration services for the seamless switchover of mission-critical business processes. It is **assumed** that the transition from traditional backup methods to combined solutions based on real-time replication and automated clustering makes it possible, simultaneously, to reduce the total cost of infrastructure ownership and to increase system availability up to the “five nines” level (99.999%).

Materials and Methods

The study relies on 24 sources, including official vendor documentation, analytical reports, and scholarly and professional publications published primarily between 2023 and 2026, with several earlier foundational sources [2].

A comparative analysis of replication architecture patterns constituted the second key component of the methodology. Particular attention was paid to comparing the capabilities of SAP HANA System Replication (HSR) and

Oracle Data Guard from the standpoint of performance and adaptability in hybrid cloud environments [7]. The case-study method made it possible to investigate in detail the processes of heterogeneous migration on the basis of practical experience in transferring IT landscapes from IBM AIX (PowerPC) platforms to SUSE Linux Enterprise Server (x86_64) using SAP HANA on VMware [10].

The source base of the study was structured along three lines: technical specifications and vendor white papers (SAP, HPE, SUSE, AWS, Azure), ensuring the accuracy of technological characteristics; analytical reports of consulting agencies (Gartner, Forrester, IDC), forming the statistical foundation for the assessment of market trends and economic risks; and scholarly articles from peer-reviewed databases, which made it possible to integrate fundamental concepts of fault tolerance into the practical analysis. In addition, the study relied on applied data related to monitoring metrics (Prometheus/Grafana) and storage-capacity calculations, which ensured the transfer of theoretical models into the engineering domain.

Results and Discussion

The contemporary ERP market is characterized not only by the rapid growth of the cloud segment, but also by the increasing architectural complexity of enterprise solutions. The emergence of hybrid models has led to the need to rethink strategies for ensuring business continuity and cybersecurity. Under such conditions, traditional approaches based exclusively on server fault tolerance and backup copies are losing effectiveness, while comprehensive data protection at the level of

applications and integration gateways is acquiring central importance.

Particular attention is being paid to the management of vulnerabilities arising during the integration of ERP with external services and third-party applications. The expansion of functionality through APIs and cloud connectors increases the attack surface, making it necessary to implement multi-layer mechanisms for access control, encryption, and transaction auditing. In addition, legislative initiatives and standards governing the processing of personal data across different jurisdictions require ERP systems to be adapted to local security and confidentiality requirements, which complicates both the migration process and the operation of cloud-based solutions [8, 9].

Beyond the technical dimension, the significance of monitoring business processes and threat analytics is also intensifying. Modern ERP platforms include built-in tools for predictive analytics and anomaly detection, making it possible to identify suspicious operations and potential information-security incidents in a timely manner. This approach provides a higher level of enterprise resilience to external and internal risks, while also forming a foundation for the strategic planning of digital transformation under conditions of accelerated cloud integration and an expanding threat landscape.

Parallel to the growth of the ERP market, there has been a strengthening of cyber threats that require a comprehensive approach to protecting critical business data. In 2025, data theft ranked first among risks for SAP systems for the first time in three years of observation, surpassing the

threat of downtime [14]. This has necessitated a revision of traditional disaster-resilience models, incorporating not only mechanisms for post-failure recovery, but also means of ensuring data integrity and consistency during replication between nodes, as well as the monitoring of anomalous operations and the timely detection of suspicious activity.

Architectural models of high availability (HA) in the SAP ecosystem continue to rely on the principle of minimizing single points of failure (SPOF). In hybrid infrastructures, this principle is implemented by means of clustering solutions and replication of the SAP HANA DBMS through the HANA System Replication (HSR) mechanism, which ensures synchronization of data and transaction logs between the primary and secondary nodes. The different HSR modes—synchronous (SYNC), synchronous in-memory (SYNCMEM), and asynchronous (ASYNC)—make it possible to balance requirements related to business continuity, data loss, and the geographic distance between data centers. It is important to note that the effectiveness of HA scenarios is determined to a large extent by the quality of cluster managers: Pacemaker and HPE Serviceguard for Linux (SGLX) provide automated switchover with minimal downtime, while integration with SAP HANA Multitarget Replication increases reliability during data replication across different sites [4, 6].

Disaster resilience (DR) in the hybrid model is regarded as a critical element of the business-protection strategy aimed at minimizing the risks of large-scale incidents affecting an entire data center or region. The use of cloud resources for disaster recovery (Cloud DR) not only makes it

possible to accelerate service restoration, but also enables the geographic distribution of backup copies, thereby reducing vulnerability to localized catastrophes. In addition, the introduction of modern monitoring tools and predictive analytics within a hybrid infrastructure ensures the timely identification of potential threats, the optimization of switchover procedures, and the creation of a reliable basis for the strategic planning of digital transformation and enterprise resilience.

An important aspect remains the alignment of HA and DR procedures with the requirements of data-protection legislation and internal standards of corporate information security. In hybrid scenarios, this implies not only physical

and network isolation, but also control over data integrity, operation logging, and automated notification of events, all of which substantially reduce incident risk and increase confidence in the digital infrastructure on the part of stakeholders. Taken together, these measures create a comprehensive ERP protection system capable of withstanding contemporary cyber threats and ensuring the continuity of critical business processes in a rapidly changing landscape of information risks.

For the sake of clarity, Table 1 presents a comparison of architectural models used to ensure SAP resilience in a hybrid environment.

Table 1. Comparison of architectural models for ensuring SAP resilience in a hybrid environment (compiled by the author based on [3])

Parameter	Active-Passive (Hot Standby)	Active-Active (Read-Enabled)	Multi-Tier (Cascading) Replication
Application	Basic fault tolerance	Load optimization	Global protection (HA + DR)
RPO (Recovery Point Objective)	0 (synchronous)	0 (synchronous)	0 (local) / >0 (remote)
RTO (Recovery Time Objective)	Minutes	Seconds	Depends on the level of failure
Resource utilization	Secondary node remains idle	Secondary node reads data	Flexible distribution
Cost (TCO)	+22% relative to baseline	+28–32% relative to baseline	+47% and above

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Within the multi-tier model, synchronous replication from the primary node to a local HA node ensures immediate restoration of services in the event of failures within a single availability zone, without affecting transaction performance. Simultaneous asynchronous replication to a remote DR node guarantees data preservation during large-scale incidents, including the failure of an entire region, thereby creating a reliable foundation for business continuity. Such an approach combines the advantages of local high availability and geographically distributed disaster resilience, making it possible to minimize data loss and downtime even in extreme scenarios.

Backup continues to remain a key instrument for protection against logical corruption, user errors, and software failures that are not eliminated by replication mechanisms. Optimization of RPO (Recovery Point Objective) and RTO (Recovery Time Objective) indicators is achieved through a carefully designed combination of full, incremental, differential backups and transaction-log backups. Such a

multi-layer approach makes it possible to ensure data consistency at every level and to respond flexibly to different types of incidents, from accidental changes to large-scale infrastructure failures.

For the effective planning and management of backups in cloud environments, specialized formulas are applied to calculate the required storage volumes while taking into account database growth, the frequency and type of backups, and RPO/RTO requirements. These methodologies make it possible to balance economic efficiency and reliability, preventing excessive resource consumption while ensuring system readiness for recovery at critical moments. Taken together, competent management of replication and backup processes forms a resilient ERP architecture capable of withstanding contemporary threats and sustaining business-process continuity in a rapidly changing information environment. The formulas for calculating storage resources for SAP HANA are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Formulas for calculating storage resources for SAP HANA (compiled by the author based on [15-18])

Volume Type	Size Calculation Formula (GiB)	Target IOPS	Throughput (MB/s)
HANA Data	$MROUND(RAM * 1.2, 100)$	$MROUND(7200 + 0.45 * RAM, 100)$	$MIN(MROUND(450 + 0.2 * RAM, 125), 2000)$
HANA Log	$MROUND(RAM * 0.5, 100)$	3000 (baseline)	$MIN(MROUND(300 + 0.015 * RAM, 300), 500)$

HANA Shared	MIN(RAM, 1024)	3000	125
Backup Storage	(Data + Log) * Retention Cycle	Depends on the backup window	Depends on channel bandwidth

The importance of choosing an optimal backup strategy is manifested not only in reducing the amount of storage consumed, but also in lowering the costs of storing and transmitting data in hybrid cloud environments. Thus, the use of a combination of full and incremental backups for a 10 TB database makes it possible to reduce the required storage volume by almost five times, which directly increases operational cost efficiency and reduces the load on network channels during replication and recovery [19]. In addition, a properly structured backup scheme simplifies archive management, accelerates recovery processes, and ensures data consistency when operating in distributed and hybrid environments.

Heterogeneous migration, including the transition from IBM AIX architecture to SUSE Linux Enterprise Server, constitutes a complex process that combines the transfer of the operating system, DBMS, and applications. Of particular complexity are differences in processor architecture (endianness) and data-

storage formats, which require careful planning and compatibility checks for custom code, SAP versions, and third-party modules. At the analysis stage, three key levels are taken into account—infrastructure, databases, and applications—which makes it possible to identify potential risk points and minimize the probability of downtime and data loss [11, 13]. The SAP SUM DMO (Database Migration Option) tool plays a critical role in heterogeneous migrations by enabling simultaneous system upgrade and database migration, thereby substantially reducing the downtime window and lowering the risks associated with manual intervention [20]. The use of such automated solutions, together with multi-layer analysis and testing, forms a structured migration approach that ensures reliability, predictability, and manageability of transformation processes for mission-critical ERP systems under conditions of transition to new technological platforms (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Three-level analysis and monitoring hierarchy for mission-critical SAP environments (author's development).

Practical experience in the implementation of hybrid ERP environments demonstrates that migration from the IBM AIX platform to SUSE Linux Enterprise Server with the SAP HANA DBMS deployed on VMware virtualization not only makes it possible to significantly improve system performance-the average enhancement in Query Response Time amounts to approximately 32%-but also increases operational flexibility through live virtual-machine migration functions (vMotion), which minimize service downtime [10]. Such an approach creates the possibility of dynamically redistributing resources among nodes without interrupting business processes, which is critical for organizations with stringent requirements for operational continuity.

The effectiveness of a hybrid infrastructure depends directly on the precision of monitoring configuration and on the proper calibration of

metrics. The use of the Prometheus and Grafana stack on the SUSE Linux Enterprise Server operating system makes it possible to visualize cluster status in real time and to minimize the number of false positives [21, 22]. Recommended settings include tracking “Effective Memory Resident” for the HANA in-memory database, monitoring replication status via REPLICATION_STATUS with immediate alert generation when values such as “ERROR” or “UNKNOWN” appear, as well as establishing network latency thresholds between HA/DR sites in order to avoid degradation of synchronous replication when acceptable latency is exceeded (1.5 ms) [23, 24].

The choice of tools for migration and system copying plays a key role in the overall success of the project. SAP SUM DMO provides simultaneous system update and database migration, thereby reducing the downtime

window and increasing process reliability, whereas SAP SWPM (Software Provisioning Manager) is oriented toward the installation and transfer of local systems without integration with support-package upgrades. A comparative analysis of these tools makes it possible to determine the optimal migration path while taking into account the architecture of the source

system, business-continuity requirements, and the volume of custom solutions, which reduces risks, increases predictability of outcomes, and ensures the economic efficiency of transformation. For greater clarity, Table 3 presents the results of a comparison of SAP migration tools.

Table 3. Comparative characteristics of SAP migration tools (compiled by the author based on [20]).

Characteristic	SAP SUM with DMO	Software Provisioning Manager (SWPM)
Primary purpose	Update + Migration (One-step)	Installation, Copying, Migration (Classical)
Process complexity	Low (automated)	High (manual export/import steps)
Downtime window	Minimal	Significant
Flexibility (SID/Hostname)	SID remains unchanged	Full flexibility of name changes
Platform support	Target HANA / ASE	Any OS and DB (AnyDB)
Error risk	Reduced due to a unified tool	Higher because of fragmented stages

Analysis of the data confirms that, in migration to S/4HANA, the DMO tool retains primary importance by ensuring high data integrity and minimizing downtime. Its use is especially effective in heterogeneous migration scenarios, where system upgrade, database transfer, and adaptation of custom solutions must be combined within a single process. This approach

makes it possible to reduce operational risks, increase predictability of the result, and optimize expenditures on technical resources.

At the same time, contemporary models of high availability and disaster resilience face a number of fundamental barriers and limitations. A shortage of qualified specialists in infrastructure as code (IaC) and hybrid-cloud orchestration is

acknowledged by 78% of technical teams, which complicates the implementation and support of complex HA/DR scenarios. Hidden costs associated with cloud DR may rise by 28–47% because of charges for data transfer and the reservation of computing resources [3], while in certain industries legislative restrictions prohibit the placement of data in public clouds, thereby requiring the creation of costly private sites for disaster recovery.

A promising direction is the broader integration of AI assistants and agentic AI capabilities into ERP operations, including SAP Joule, which may eventually support more proactive continuity

management [5, 12]. Such solutions, including tools such as SAP Joule, make it possible to implement predictive failover and gradually transform the approach to managing business-process continuity, thereby forming the foundation for a reliable, self-learning ERP infrastructure by 2027. For the visual representation of the complex processes involved in transition from legacy platforms, the author’s flowchart of heterogeneous migration (Figure 2) reflects the sequence of stages of analysis, preparation, and execution of system transformation.

Figure 2. Workflow of heterogeneous migration from legacy platforms to hybrid SAP HANA environment (author's development).

This scheme underscores that the validation phase and the three-level analysis (infrastructure, database, and application layer) constitute the key node that determines system stability and reliability after migration. At this stage, the compatibility of custom code, the correctness of replication configuration, and the alignment of high-availability parameters with business requirements are verified. Validation makes it possible to identify potential points of failure, deviations in module behavior, and inconsistencies in HA/DR settings, which significantly reduces the risks of unforeseen downtime and data loss.

In addition, the three-level analysis ensures the integration of monitoring, backup, and disaster-resilience procedures into a single manageable model. This makes it possible to align RPO and RTO indicators with the architectural characteristics of the system, assess the load imposed on network and computing resources, and optimize the recovery plan for incident scenarios. Thus, the successful completion of this phase becomes critically important for achieving ERP infrastructure resilience, especially in hybrid and distributed scenarios.

Finally, the results of the analysis form the foundation for subsequent stages of transformation, including failover automation, the introduction of predictive AI-based mechanisms, and adaptation to regulatory requirements. A comprehensive approach to validation makes it possible not only to minimize operational risks, but also to create a predictable, scalable, and economically efficient architecture capable of withstanding both current and future cyber threats, while ensuring the continuity of

critical business processes.

Conclusion

Within the framework of the study conducted, a comprehensive analysis was carried out of architectural models for ensuring the high availability and disaster resilience of SAP systems in a hybrid infrastructure. The results made it possible to identify several key propositions. The integration of native DBMS replication mechanisms, such as HSR and Data Guard, with external clustering tools, for example HPE Serviceguard, has been recognized as the most reliable approach for achieving virtually zero RPO and RTO indicators in a hybrid environment. Migration to the SUSE Linux Enterprise Server platform during transition from AIX provides technological consistency with cloud nodes and opens access to advanced monitoring tools, including Prometheus and Grafana, which substantially reduces the number of false alarms generated by alerting systems.

The optimization of backup strategies through the use of incremental models and refined storage-calculation methods makes it possible to reduce cloud-infrastructure costs by up to 80% while preserving the required level of reliability. Heterogeneous migration with the use of SUM DMO has demonstrated its effectiveness in the modernization of legacy IT landscapes, ensuring the unification of application upgrade and platform transition within a single manageable process.

The practical value of the study lies in providing engineers and architects with ready-to-use calculation formulas and proven architectural patterns. The hypothesis concerning the

advantages of hybrid resilience models has been confirmed by data demonstrating a 71.2% reduction in downtime and a decrease in operational expenses when cloud DR is employed. The implementation of the proposed solutions will allow enterprises to ensure

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business-process continuity under the conditions of the increasingly complex cyber landscape of 2025, while the materials presented are of clear interest to the professional community engaged in designing next-generation systems.

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